

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EZAMA****FIRST NAME: ARNOLD****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student used *Turabian/Chicago writing style*.

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 12%

The author used the MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the correct order of front matter components in a dissertation?
- Title page; Copyright page; Abstract; Dedication; Acknowledgments; Table of contents; List of tables and figures.¹**
 - Title page; Dedication; Acknowledgments; Copyright page; Table of contents; List of tables and figures; and Abstract.
 - Title page; Dedication; Copyright page; Abstract; Acknowledgments; Table of contents; and List of Tables and Figures.
 - Title page; Abstract; Copyright page; Acknowledgments; Table of contents; and List of tables and figures.

1. Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 64–73.

2. Which of the statements is associated with notes-style?
- Notes are indented like other paragraphs in the text: the first line of each note is indented, and anything that runs over to a new line is flush left.²**
 - In notes, separate most elements with periods; in bibliography entries, separate them with commas.
 - In notes, facts of publication are not enclosed in parentheses; while in bibliography entries, they are enclosed in parentheses.
 - For source materials with only one author, when citing in-text, within the parenthesis, the author's first name is written first, then the year, and finally, the pages.
3. Which one of the statements below is correct about the literature review process?
- The literature review is found in chapter three of the dissertation.
 - A literature review of a research topic takes on a narrow to wider perspective.
 - A conceptual or theoretical framework results from reviewing the literature; this guides data collection and analysis.³**
 - After developing a theoretical or conceptual framework diagrammatic model, it is not always necessary to accompany it with a comprehensive descriptive narrative.
4. According to the prose for American English, which sentence is correct?

2. Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 155.

3. Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 413.

- Our teacher said, “let all the people who said ‘yes’ to the question organise the classroom.”
 - Our teacher said, ‘let all the people who said “yes” to the question organize the classroom’.
 - Our teacher said, ‘let all the people who said ‘yes’ to the question organise the classroom.”
 - Our teacher said, “let all the people who said ‘yes’ to the question organize the classroom.”⁴**
5. Which of the statements is correct about the philosophical paradigms?
- A constructivist’s ontological perspective refers to a single reality, while the postpositivist’s ontological perspective refers to multiple realities.
 - A constructivist is an instrument in data collection and interpretation of the research findings while playing an emic role.⁵**
 - Epistemology refers to what values go into knowing what we know.
 - Methodology refers to techniques, procedures, and tools for generating and analyzing data.
6. Which of the statements about qualitative study traditions is wrong?

4. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 24–34.

5. Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 149.

- A case study is an in-depth study of cases or phenomena using multiple data sources.
 - Phenomenology: investigates lived experience of study participants and looks at essence common to different happenings.
 - Ethnography is a methodology where the researcher is at risk of going native lives for an extended period with the study participants in their community and applies reflexivity in interpreting the findings.
 - Grounded theory is deductive and descriptive, where the researcher studies commonly understood phenomena.⁶**
7. Which of the sentences is unacceptable when using the WHO writing style?
- WHO documents use a mix of British and North American spelling.
 - Capitalize the initial letter for formal titles before the names, and one should not separate the title and the name using a comma.
 - When generating a list of names, courtesy titles such as Mr. or Ms. are unnecessary; write the names without those titles; but only indicate Dr., Professor, and other titles to persons with them.⁷**
 - In a sentence, leaving no space between the figure and the symbol is acceptable.
8. During the process of writing a dissertation, which one of the statements is wrong?

6. Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 171.

7. World Health Organization, *WHO style guide* (Geneva: WHO Press 2013), 23.

- Start with generating a working hypothesis to help you formulate appropriate claims.
 - To make a solid argument, one needs to state the claim, followed by the reason for the claim, back up the reasoning with evidence, acknowledge alternative points of view, and give a warrant.
 - Apply warrants to answer those who might or do not understand how your reasons are relevant to your claim.
 - Please write the dissertation title before you start the dissertation writing process; it is best not to change it frequently.⁸**
9. To get trustworthy results, which of the sentences below should a researcher follow when deciding what study methodology to use?
- From the beginning, the researcher should start by understanding the data collection and analysis process before deciding which study methodology to use.
 - From the beginning, the researcher should reflect on the research problem, then consider the data collection and analysis process, then finally consider what methodology to apply.
 - From the beginning, the researcher should reflect on the study problem, develop a working hypothesis, choose the study approach, consider the study strategy/tradition to guide feasible data collection, and analyze.⁹**

8. Turabian et al, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 166.

9. Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 135.

- From the beginning, the researcher should reflect on the resources needed to complete the study, like time, finances, and availability of technical support, then choose a study methodology.

10. Which of these statements is not correct?

- It is not plagiarism if you use words from a source and cite the source.**¹⁰
- It is not plagiarism if you take ideas from a source and cite the source.
- It is not plagiarism if you refer to commonly known quotes from the Bible and do not cite the source within the write-up and Bibliography.
- It is preferable to cite the primary source instead of the secondary source.

10. Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 36. The words should be paraphrased; if you use the words from the source, then apply quotation marks.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago ; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.